

Sub-network Merging in Self-Managed VANETs

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Abstract

The most widespread wireless technology for mobile ad-hoc networks nowadays is Wi-Fi technology based on IEEE 802.11xx protocol. The structure of this protocol produces some problems when sub-networks try to merge. Two reasons that can cause inability to communicate are IP duplication and the existence of sub-networks on different channels. In the bibliography some theoretical solutions have been mentioned and tested through simulation, but not with real devices. Here a practical solution is fully described and implemented in a new tool developed to create a vehicular ad-hoc network by using only mobile devices. As for the choice of the sub-networks to merge, first a simple and deterministic algorithm is proposed, and then, interferences between wireless channels are taken into account under a fuzzy logic point of view. Promising results are obtained from the security and performance analysis of large scale NS2 simulations based on data obtained from implementations with real devices.

Keywords: Sub-networks, Channels, VANET, MANET, Merging, IEEE 802.11xx, Interferences, Fuzzy logic.

1 Introduction

A Vehicular Ad-hoc NETWORK (VANET) is a form of Mobile Ad-hoc NETWORK (MANET) used to provide communications between vehicles to increase comfort and safety in every day road travels.

The IEEE 802.11 protocol is used in most existing MANETs to use Wi-Fi connection, what enables short-to-medium-range wireless communication capability (up to 300 m). In these networks, each device first checks whether some wireless network exists in its neighbourhood or not. Then, if the network exists, the device tries to connect to it, and otherwise, the device creates a new wireless network.

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The creation of wireless networks in real environments can cause trouble mainly due to the spontaneous formation of sub-networks. The two most important problems appear when two or more sub-networks cannot see each other because they are on different channels, or two or more sub-networks use the same channel but there are devices with the same IP address. The most usual problem is the first one because the choice of the wireless channel is random. The solution implies that the sub-networks have to be on the same channel and with no IP address conflict to merge with no problem. However, this case is unusual spontaneously.

Channels with the lower numbers use lower frequencies, and with lower frequency propagation is better because there is less attenuation. Though, the problem of the difference in attenuation is not comparable with the loss of packets in the channel due to the interference between networks in adjacent channels. There are channels that are more saturated than others. That is the case of channels 6 and 11. Also interferences exist with Bluetooth and other systems using the 2.4 GHz ISM (Industrial, Scientific and Medical) band. The broadcasting channels that are more common in the IEEE 802.11xx protocol are type a, b, g and n. Its range is from channels 1 to 11 in America, 1 to 13 in Europe and 1 to 14 in Japan. Channels share part of their bandwidth.

Figure 1: Channels

Figure 1 shows the channels that the devices in Europe can choose to create a wireless network, remarking the maximum number of channels that can be used without interference. In particular five is the maximum number of simultaneous wireless networks without interference.

The various versions of the IEEE 802.11xx protocol provide the advantage of being compatible with each other, so that the user does not need anything more than its integrated Wi-Fi adapter to connect to the network. However, too much saturation in one channel can cause packet collisions in the data transfer, what corresponds to a lower transfer rate and/or speed.

1.1 Related Work

There are several projects on VANETs and MANETs that assume wireless communication via Wi-Fi. However, most studies are rather theoretical. Some of them include simulations using tools such as NS2 [2] or OPNET [5], while very few have implementations in real environments [6]. In the present work, both methods have been used to check the proposal by combining software simulations with data obtained from implementations in real devices.

Some papers, like [8], discusses the sub-network merging process in the event of an IP address conflict problem. Others try to solve different problems regarding channels in ad-hoc networks. These are the cases of [18], where the authors

try to use multiple channels simultaneously, [1], which shows a way to estimate and avoid the noise in the channel by using fuzzy logic, and [9], which analyzes the impact of channel estimation errors due to noise and interference. The authors in [19] propose a heuristic polynomial time algorithm to eliminate interferences. [20] proposes a framework for multi-radio multi-channel cognitive wireless networks to maximize a network utility function based on data routing, resource allocation and scheduling. In the specific case of wireless mesh networks, several are the works that deal with the channel assignment problem. [15] studies the assignment of non-overlapping channels in those networks by minimizing interference while improving the network capacity and maintaining the connectivity of the network. Also the same problem in mesh networks, the presence of interference from collocated wireless networks is addressed in [14]. There the authors propose a dynamic centralized interference-aware algorithm aimed at improving the capacity of the backbone and minimizing interference. Their proposal is based on an extension to the conflict graph concept described in [11], where the vertices represent edges between mesh radios instead of edges between mesh routers.

Several works face different problems in the IEEE 802.11 protocol. For instance, [4] proposes an application that uses Bluetooth technology to solve the configuration problem of the terminals in an IEEE 802.11-based ad-hoc network by extending the connectivity range of nodes through packet forwarding. In [7] the authors do a performance analysis of the 802.11b protocol in such configurations using an analytical modelling technique. [10] proposes a protection scheme for DoS (Denial of Service) attacks in the 802.11 protocol for WEP, WPA and WPA2. The authors of [12] do a study of the relationship between clock synchronization and power-saving in IEEE 802.11-like mobile ad hoc networks. Finally, [13] proposes and simulates an algorithm to mitigate the Bluetooth interference with the channel estimation stage in IEEE 802.11g.

All the above proposals try to solve different problems of the IEEE 802.11 protocol but none of them follows the same approach of the present paper. The closest work is [17] on multi-hop ad hoc networks using conventional IEEE 802.11 where long transient resynchronisation states are often generated. The authors propose a modification of the resynchronisation that reduces times and energy consumption. However, such a work does not include any implementation in real devices, what is one of the main aspects of the present paper.

1.2 Our Contribution

VAiPho (VANET in Phones) [3] is a new tool for creating VANETs by using only mobile devices playing the role of On-Board Units (OBUs) in vehicles. It automatically detects in real time different types of events such as traffic jams and sends warnings about them to other mobile devices via Wi-Fi in order to give drivers an augmented reality about road conditions. A fundamental requirement for this tool is that each mobile device is both client and server, and connects to the same wireless network.

In VANETs implemented through VAIpho, when two instances of the same

wireless network exist on different channels, the so-called sub-network merging problem arises and has to be solved. The ideal solution would imply that the largest sub-network absorbs the smallest one, but nodes do not know the size of other sub-networks. This work describes first a generic algorithm to compute the minimum time that any device of a sub-network requires to reset and to connect with other sub-network, depending on the size of its sub-network. Then, fuzzy logic rules are used to interpret interferences between channels in terms of sizes of neighbour sub-networks in order to allow that larger sub-networks absorb smaller ones. One of the key points of this paper is the performance analysis of large scale NS2 simulations based on data obtained from implementations with real devices of the proposals.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces a generic deterministic proposal. In Section 3, a fuzzy logic based approach is proposed. Section 4 includes a performance analysis of such a proposal by using real devices and a large scale NS2 simulation. In Section 5 a security analysis of the proposal is included. Finally, Section 6 includes some conclusions and open problems.

2 Generic Sub-network Merging Protocol

In order to solve the sub-network merging problem, this paper proposes to reset the wireless interface of the devices that belong to all but one of the wireless sub-networks. The optimal solution would imply resetting those sub-networks that have a lower number of devices, but this information is not transparent to the devices of each sub-network, which can know only the number of devices in their sub-network, and not in other sub-networks.

If a node detects an IP address conflict, it resets its network interface and this is enough to solve the problem. However, the problem is much more difficult to solve when the existence of sub-networks is because they are on different channels.

2.1 Basic Scheme

A first approximation of the solution is based on choosing the sub-networks in the most appropriate channel to minimize the interference created by the networks on adjacent channels (see Algorithm 1). To do this, each device regularly checks for existing sub-networks used by neighbour nodes. Those vehicles with an OBU, which can be either a laptop or a mobile phone running *VAiPho* application, are considered the nodes of the VANET. If there are two instances of the network called *vaiPho*, all the devices belonging to one of the sub-networks have to reset their wireless interfaces. The first node that detects this situation sends a warning message to the remaining nodes of the network so that they restart its wireless interface. Thus, upon receipt, the nodes broadcast the message, turn off their network interface for 1 second and reactivate it. Then, since a *vaiPho* network already exists when they restart, the nodes will connect to this network and the problem will be solved. The nodes will remain authenticated

by the nodes of the previous sub-network because authentication data do not vary with the change of sub-network, which has exactly the same name, *vaipho*.

Algorithm 1 Choosing the sub-network with less interference

```

00: ...
01: //several vaipho networks exist
02: int[] channelDifference = new int[nNetworks];
03: //channelDifference stores the difference between channels.
04: for (int i = 0; i < vaiphoInstances; i++)
05:   channelDifference[i] = 50;
06: for (int i = 0; i < nNetworks; i++)
07:   for (int j = 0; j < nNetworks; j++)
08:     if (network[i].Equals(wifi)) //compare sub-network with others
09:       if ((i != j) &&
10:           (Math.Abs(channel[i] - channel[j])) < channelDifference[i])
11:         channelDifference[i] = Math.Abs(channel[i] - channel[j]);
12: //the channel with biggest difference between channels is not reset
13: for (int i = 0; i < nNetworks; i++)
14:   if ((biggestDifference < channelDifference[i])
15:       &&(channelDifference[i]!=50)) //store the biggest difference
16:     biggestDifference = channelDifference[i];
17:     nodeLocationBiggestDifference = i;
18:   if (nodeLocationBiggestDifference != numberOwnNetwork)
19:     //if my network has not the biggest interference
20:     networkDetachProtocol(wifi);
21:   return true;
22: ...

```

2.2 Optimized Choice

When several devices belonging to different sub-networks are neighbours, each device can determine the existence of other sub-networks. In order to enable the deployment of VANETs through VAiPho, each device has to check whether other vaipho sub-networks exist in its transmission range. Thus, if different sub-networks exist with the same name because they were created independently on different channels, these sub-networks must be merged to allow that the separate sub-networks become one. Each member of one of the sub-networks that discovers the problem must choose a new channel to include the members of both previous channels. In particular, according to [16] the devices that are in the sub-network with the largest number of channel will restart their network interfaces because the new channel of the merged sub-networks will be the smallest number of all previous channels. However, such a procedure to choose the surviving sub-network is not optimal because it does not depend on the number of nodes in such a sub-network, or the interferences between channels used by other wireless networks.

Each device can only know the number of nodes that are in its sub-network, the channel where it is, in which channels there are other instances of the *vaipho* network, and the channels that are being used by other networks that can interfere with its *vaipho* sub-network. However, the interference in channels can be used to determine the sub-network that will be restarted.

Figure 2 shows a typical example of a VANET in an urban scenario where two sub-networks of vehicles denoted A and B enter the same transmission range and find out that two *vaipho* instances were formed on different channels while there are interferences with other wireless networks. Each node of a sub-network that can see nodes of other sub-networks checks the channel where its sub-network is and the channels of the remaining sub-networks, and analyze possible interferences with other wireless networks. In Figure 2 the sub-network A is on channel 1, B is on channel 6, and there are two other wireless networks on channels 2 and 4. Therefore, the channel of A is at distance 1 from the nearest network (channel 2), and the channel of B is at distance 2 from the nearest network (channel 4). Thus, there should be concluded that the channel of the sub-network A has more interference possibilities, and so those devices should restart to merge with sub-network B.

Figure 2: Example of a usual situation

However, as aforementioned, the optimal solution should consist in resetting the sub-networks with fewer devices. Thus, in the next section a new fuzzy logic approach is proposed as closer to the optimal solution.

3 Fuzzy Logic Based Sub-network Merging

The number of generated and lost packets during a merging process will be always lower if the sub-network whose devices restart its network interface is the sub-network with fewer nodes, as can be seen in Figure 3. From this starting point, we tried to develop a heuristic method that, without knowing the number of nodes in other sub-networks, allows that the sub-network with fewer devices is the sub-network whose nodes restart their wireless interfaces. In addition, another important factor that is also taken into account is the interference with the channels of other existing sub-networks.

Figure 3: Number of generated and lost packets

A fuzzy logic approach is used to compute the time that each node has to wait before checking whether the problem remains unsolved or not, so that in the first case it restarts and begins the merging process. For the estimation of such a time not only the number of nodes in each sub-network is taken into account but also a correction factor based on the interference between channels. Two objectives of the waiting time computation are that the times should be minimized and that the nodes belonging to the chosen sub-network should not restart their interface because that would imply that all nodes would restart their interfaces, and in that case the process would not be optimal.

The time $A(x)$ that each node has to wait before checking whether it has to restart and join another sub-network is first expressed in terms of the number x of nodes in its sub-network. For the fuzzy logic approach, the times shown in Figure 4 were computed with real devices. This time can be either linearly approximated by the Equation 1, where S_r is the residual standard deviation that measures the average variability of the data about the regression line, or represented by the logarithmic Equation 2.

$$A(x) = 0.107 x + 3.63 \pm S_r \text{ if } x > 0 \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Time relay for sub-network merging

$$A(x) = 6.2454 \ln(x) - 0.6499 \pm S_r \text{ if } x > 0 \quad (2)$$

These expressions have been used as starting points to estimate the optimum time before checking whether there are multiple *vaipho* instances. In particular, this paper proposes the use of the linear expression by removing the initial constant time 3.63. In this way, a node detecting that there are multiple instances of the *vaipho* network will wait for a time determined by the number of nodes in its sub-network characterized by the formula $W(x) = 0.107x$. For instance, a node detecting multiple instances of the *vaipho* network such that its sub-network is composed of 2 nodes, will wait for 0.214 seconds before rechecking whether there are more than one *vaipho* instance, and another node detecting the same but belonging to a sub-network of 20 nodes will wait for 2.14 seconds before rechecking. In this way, the smallest sub-networks would always join the largest sub-networks.

Apart from taking into account the number of nodes in each sub-network, it is convenient that for sub-networks with similar size, the interference between channels is also considered so that the sub-network with less interference prevails over the others.

A sub-network operating on a channel is said to have no interference if no other sub-network is operating on the same channel or in less than two channels away from it. The interference power of a channel c can be measured in dBc ,

which is a unit used to express the absolute power of a network signal with a power level P , through the logarithmic Equation 3.

$$dBc = 10 \log \frac{P}{1mW} \quad (3)$$

By using this metric, the interference $I(c)$ that a network using a channel c has can be estimated through the Equation 4, where N denotes the number of sub-networks using the same channel c , M and Q denote respectively the numbers of sub-networks within 1 or 2 channels of distance from channel c , and a is obtained from the expression $\frac{2a}{dBc_{high}} = 1$ where dBc_{high} corresponds to the channel with highest interference.

$$I(c) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{-a}{dBc_i} + \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{2(-a)}{3dBc_j} + \sum_{k=1}^Q \frac{-a}{3dBc_k} \quad (4)$$

The above expression results from the fact that if two sub-networks operate on the same channel the overlap is total, if they are in adjacent channels the overlap is 2/3 of the frequency they use, and if they are two channels away the overlap is 1/3 of the frequency they use. Note that the value of a could vary depending on the place where vehicles are because if they are in a location where there are many wireless networks, the possibility of having more than two sub-networks using the same channel is higher.

At this point the use of a fuzzy logic based approach for the application of the above interference between channels of sub-networks is proposed to estimate the waiting times for checking and resetting.

From real data, the expression that defines a degree of interference B for a *vaipho* instance depending on the interference d of the own sub-network can be estimated according to the Equation 5 when no interference with other wireless networks exists, and by the Equation 6 when interference with other wireless networks exists.

$$B(d) = \begin{cases} \emptyset & \text{if } d > 0 \\ 1 + 0.1\hat{1}d & \text{if } d \in (0, -90) \\ 1 & \text{if } d < -90 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$B(d) = \begin{cases} \emptyset & \text{if } d > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } d \in (0, -10) \\ -0,005(d + 10) & \text{if } d \in (-10, -230) \\ 1 & \text{if } d < -210 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The proposed method allows to consider the degree of interference between two instances of the *vaipho* network to estimate the waiting time for the sub-network merging. Figure 5 shows an estimation of such a degree of interference depending both on the power of the network and the existence of interferences with other networks as expressed in the above equations.

Figure 5: Fuzzy logic approach of sub-network merging

From the above figure, in the design of the rules of fuzzy control, denoted below by Rule 1 and Rule 2, which depend on the interferences of the network of the node performing the test, denoted by $vaipho(\alpha)$, and of the other sub-networks, denoted by $vaipho(\beta(l))$ where $l \geq 1$. $F(x)$ is used to store the time that the x nodes of the sub-network $vaipho(\alpha)$ wait before checking again whether the other *vaipho* instances exist. If a different *vaipho* instance exists after its waiting time, the node that detects it, starts the merging protocol, otherwise, the node does not restart its interface. Rule 2 is always tested after Rule 1 to determine the time that is added or subtracted to the waiting time $F(x)$.

Rule 1 Own instance of the *vaipho* network

if $(I(vaipho(\alpha)) > -10)$ **then** //With interference

$$F(x) = W(x) + \frac{DI(vaipho(\alpha))}{2}$$

else //Without interference

$$F(x) = W(x) - \frac{DI(vaipho(\alpha))}{2}$$

Rule 2 Other instances of the *vaipho* network

if $(I(vaipho(\beta(l))) < -90)$ **then** //Without interference

$$F(x) = F(x) - \frac{DI(vaipho(\beta(l)))}{2}$$

else //With interference

$$F(x) = F(x) + \frac{DI(vaipho(\beta(l)))}{2}$$

According to the above proposal, each sub-network $vaipho(\alpha)$ with x nodes estimates its own waiting time $F(x)$ having into account not only its own data

but also another sub-network $vaipho(\beta(l))$ data, such as its channel and the remaining channels affecting it.

Figure 6 shows the waiting time that a node has to wait before rechecking $vaipho$ interfaces. This time depends on the number of nodes of the corresponding sub-network and on the interferences in the channels where $vaipho(\alpha)$ and $vaipho(\beta(l))$ are.

Figure 6: Waiting time depending on the interferences

4 Performance Evaluation

In this section an implementation analysis of the above proposals is included. To check the effectiveness of the sub-network merging process, the best option would be that large scale sub-networks with real devices merge. However, doing this with a large number of devices is not easy. Therefore the chosen alternative has been to implement the scheme in real devices, taking real data of reconnection and merging, and then using those real data in a simulation with NS2.

4.1 Real Device Implementation

The implementation in real devices has been developed by using mobile phones with Windows Mobile 5 and 6 (see Table 1). The used platform was Microsoft Visual Studio 2008. Algorithm 2 shows the first phase corresponding to the detection of other sub-networks.

Algorithm 2 Sub-network detection

```

00: function CheckingSubnetworks (...)
01:   ...
02:   foreach (AccessPoint access in wzc.NearbyAccessPoints)
03:     network[nNetworks] = access.Name.ToString();

```

Table 1: Mobile devices

Phone name	Platform	CPU Speed	RAM	ROM	Battery capacity
HTC HD Mini	WM 6.5	600 MHz	384 MB	512 MB	1200 mAh
HTC P3300	WM 5.0	201 MHz	64 MB	128 MB	1250 mAh
HTC Touch2	WM 6.5	528 MHz	256 MB	512 MB	1100 mAh
hp IPAQ 614C	WM 6.0	520 MHz	128 MB	256 MB	1590 mAh

```

04:   channels[nNetworks] = access.Channel;
05:   MacAddress[nNetworks] = access.PhysicalAddress.ToString();
06:   if (network[nNetworks].Equals(wifi))
07:       VaiphoInstances++;
08:       //store the n of channel with the biggest network
09:       if (channels[nNetworks] > biggestChannel)
10:           biggestChannel = channels[nNetworks];
11:       //save the network where we are
12:       if (MacAddress[nNetworks].ToString().Equals(MacOwnAddress))
13:           numberOwnNetwork = nNetworks;
14:       nNetworks++;
15: ...

```

A screenshot of two emulators that use the same *vaipho* sub-network while there is another *vaipho* sub-network in another channel is shown in Figure 7. In this example the device on the right is the first one to detect the presence of multiple instances of the network *vaipho*. After checking that there are other *vaipho* instances, this node starts the merging protocol. In the merging protocol, the node that detects the *vaipho* sub-networks sends the warning message to the remaining nodes of the sub-network to make they restart their network interfaces. After that, every node turns off its interface for some time and then reactivates its network interface, and connects to the *vaipho* network that already exists.

Figure 8 shows several wireless networks in the transmission range. In particular, it can be seen that there are two instances of the *vaipho* network, the first one is on channel 1 while the second one is on channel 11. It can be also seen that there are other networks on channels 1 and 11. Such a situation implies the need of sub-network merging.

4.2 Large Scale Simulation

In order to check the average time that it would take any sub-network to integrate into another sub-network, different NS2 simulations of the sub-network merging proposals were carried out for different sub-network sizes. The time that the devices take to restart their network interface and connect to the other

Figure 7: Real device implementation

instance of the network on the correct channel was taken from the implementations with real devices, by using the average. The times ranging from 2.94 seconds were recorded as the best case for the HTC HD Mini, and 9.15 seconds was recorded as the worst case for the HTC P3300. Therefore, the implementation produced a range between 2.94 and 9.15 seconds to reset the network interface. The times that depend on the used authentication protocol were not included. Thus, the considered time only includes the time it takes to shut down the network interface plus the time for the waiting process, and the time to reconnect the device to the existing *vaipho* network. After such executions with real devices, the obtained data were used for a large scale NS2 simulation. Figure 9 shows an example of one of the simulations, in particular the simulation of a highway with three lanes. In this simulation the two sub-networks have different colours and in red colour we have the node that detects the two instances of the same network and sends the warning message to reset the network interface.

Figure 10 shows the numerical results obtained from the NS2 simulations. These simulations were performed with sub-networks of sizes between 10 and 140 nodes. We obtained the average times that nodes take to reconnect to the network with less interference. Different levels were distinguished depending on the size of the sub-network. In such a figure, we use the word 'level' to refer to the subset of nodes that are in same transmission range of the transmitter node, so the first node detecting that there are multiple instances of *vaipho* network, sends a warning message, when the warning reaches the subset of nodes that

SSID	Default Authentication	Default Encryption	RSSI (dBm)	Channel	Frequency (MHz)	BSSID (MAC Address)	Network Mode	Network Type
eduroam	WPA2/802.1x	AES-CCMP	-43	1	2412	Cisco:08:1E:F0	802.11g	Access Point
vaipho	Open	None	-34	1	2412	unknown:D7:92:8E	802.11g	Independent
welcome@HTW	Open	None	-42	1	2412	Cisco:08:1E:F5	802.11g	Access Point
Gast@HTW	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-42	1	2412	Cisco:08:1E:F3	802.11g	Access Point
Gast@HTW	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-69	11	2462	Cisco:0A:D7:93	802.11g	Access Point
eduroam	WPA2/802.1x	AES-CCMP	-69	11	2462	Cisco:0A:D7:90	802.11g	Access Point
welcome@HTW	Open	None	-71	11	2462	Cisco:0A:D7:95	802.11g	Access Point
vaipho	Open	None	-71	11	2462	unknown:C6:46:A5	802.11g	Independent
Gast@HTW	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-73	11	2462	Cisco:C6:46:A3	802.11g	Access Point
Gast@HTW	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-87	1	2412	Cisco:C6:96:43	802.11g	Access Point

Figure 8: Network instances

are closest to it, they broadcast this information and then, restart their network interfaces. Nodes that reach this information will be from another level, and so on. Figure 10 shows the average time it takes for the nodes in each transmission level to reconnect to the other *vaipho* sub-network. The simulations show a natural result, the larger the size of the sub-networks, the longer the sub-network merging time. However, if nodes are divided into transmission levels, it can be seen that it takes about the same time regardless of the number of nodes that the sub-networks have.

5 Security Analysis

The topology of VANETs does not allow guaranteeing absolute security mainly because the wireless channel is open. There are several types of attacks that both unauthenticated and authenticated nodes can perform by using the vulnerabilities of a distributed and self-managed wireless network like the VANET here analyzed.

Two main types of attacks on wireless networks can be distinguished: attacks produced by nodes that have not been authenticated (outside attacks), and those produced by authenticated nodes that belong to the network (inside attacks). In this paper, it is assumed that a strong authentication protocol prevents inside attacks.

The attacks carried out against the IEEE 802.11 protocol can be classified into passive and active attacks. Among the most important attacks, passive attacks such as sniffing and passive traffic analysis and active attacks such as impersonation and DoS are remarkable. Most passive and active attacks can be avoided with a good authentication protocol, but there are still some possible attacks to the proposed schema that must be analyzed.

DoS attacks can be performed by any malicious user who can introduce noise in the channel so that the devices can not communicate with each other

Figure 9: NS2 simulation

in the corresponding transmission range. A possible solution to this attack is the change of the channel because that produces the change in the frequency of broadcast. The scheme proposed in this paper can suffer an active and inside attack consisting in that a malicious user could create a *vaipho* instance in a different channel from the original *vaipho* sub-network to force that the other devices restart their wireless interfaces in order to connect to the false created network. So, if the malicious user changes it once again continuously, the network would be reconnecting all the time. To prevent this attack, first a strong authentication scheme is necessary. Then, a timestamp can be defined so that the devices have to wait for some time before reconnecting to a different network. This solution is not optimal but allows that the network works properly.

6 Conclusion

This paper has proposed the development of practical solutions to the problem that arises when merging several mobile wireless networks formed by mobile devices equipped with Wi-Fi by using the IEEE 802.11x protocol. A usual

Figure 10: Delay of sub-network merging

problem arises when sub-networks are created on different channels so that some nodes are not visible to other nodes. This work analyzes this topic, which has not been solved till now by the research community despite there are countless studies about MANETs and VANETs. The optimal solution would consist in that the smaller sub-networks join the largest sub-network, but there is no possibility for nodes to know the number of devices that integrate other sub-networks. Thus, this paper first proposes a generic deterministic solution based only on the number of nodes in a sub-network. Then this paper outlines a new fuzzy logic approach to estimate the time that a node has to wait before checking whether the problem has been solved or not, so that in this case it restarts its network interface, which is based both on the number of nodes in its sub-network, and data about possible interferences from other sub-networks. The proposals have been implemented in the VAIpho tool, which is being developed to create a VANET by using only mobile devices. The performance evaluation of the proposals obtained from their implementation in real devices and large scale NS2 simulation is promising as it shows how in a few seconds, all nodes of all sub-networks merge into a single network.

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Figure 1

Name: vaipho
Channel: 1

Name: vaipho
Channel: 6

A

A

B

B

A

A

A

B

B

Name: other1
Channel: 2

Name: other2
Channel: 4

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Degree of Interference

Without
With

Figure 5

Figure 6

1°

Figure 7

SSID	Default Authentication	Default Encryption	RSSI (dBm) ▲	Channel	Frequency (MHz)	BSSID (MAC Address)	Network Mode	Network Type
<u>eduroam</u>	WPA2/802.1x	AES-CCMP	-43	1	2412	Cisco:0B:1E:F0	802.11g	Access Point
<u>vaipho</u>	Open	None	-34	1	2412	unknown:D7:92:8E	802.11g	Independent
<u>welcome@HTW</u>	Open	None	-42	1	2412	Cisco:0B:1E:F5	802.11g	Access Point
<u>Gast@HTW</u>	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-42	1	2412	Cisco:0B:1E:F3	802.11g	Access Point
<u>Gast@HTW</u>	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-69	11	2462	Cisco:0A:D7:93	802.11g	Access Point
<u>eduroam</u>	WPA2/802.1x	AES-CCMP	-69	11	2462	Cisco:0A:D7:90	802.11g	Access Point
<u>welcome@HTW</u>	Open	None	-71	11	2462	Cisco:0A:D7:95	802.11g	Access Point
<u>vaipho</u>	Open	None	-71	11	2462	unknown:C6:46:A5	802.11g	Independent
<u>Gast@HTW</u>	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-73	11	2462	Cisco:C6:46:A3	802.11g	Access Point
<u>Gast@HTW</u>	WPA2/PSK	AES-CCMP	-82	1	2412	Cisco:C6:96:43	802.11g	Access Point

Figure 8

Figure 10